

A CASE STUDY ON APPROACHES TO EASY-TO READ DISCOURSES

ATAEVA GULCHEKHRA, YULDASHEVA
DILFUZA, RAKHMONOVA YULDUZ and
ATADJANOVA SEVARA

Tashkents State transport University

Abstract. In 2017, the organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development estimated that around 25 per cent of the population experiences difficulties in reading comprehension. The World Health Organisation (2021) has indicated that around 15 per cent of the world population faces functional impairment-related problems, which limit sufficient access to information unless the resources are adapted for meeting the needs of this layer of society. Considering the increasing numbers of the population who suffer from impairments at the language perception level, the present study has attempted to examine selected approaches that might serve for developing easy-to-read (EtR) discourses. Limited research has been conducted in the above-mentioned field, and the contributions that exist so far have focused on the linguistic and design features considered when producing EtR discourses; however, other central components that govern the adaptation of authentic texts for EtR needs seem to be neglected. Therefore, the present study aims to examine selected discourse-pragmatic approaches that can be applied for adapting texts to an EtR language. The present research is a qualitative case study targeted at EtR text developers and seeks to answer the research question: *which discourse-pragmatic approaches should be considered to produce easy-to-read discourses?* In conclusion, the paper offers the implications of the findings and reflects on the value of using discourse-pragmatic approaches to EtR discourse and cognitive load reduction.

Key words: discourse-pragmatic approaches, Easy language, easy-to-read discourse, adaptation, cognitive load reduction

INTRODUCTION

The paper offers some insights into selected approaches that were considered for adapting authentic texts into easy-to-read (EtR) language. The approaches under analysis require specialists' professional and academic competence, and/or experience in applying selected text discursive and text pragmatic principles for adaptation of EtR language, in addition to expertise gained in producing easy-to-read and easy-to-understand discourses.

In the context of this study, the term *Easy language* (EL) is applied as an umbrella notion that incorporates such parallel terms as easy-to-read (written texts in Easy language), easy-to-read-and-understand, and easy-to-understand language. When specific reference to written Easy language texts is made, the term EtR is used. The application of the EL can be considered as a general-purpose linguistic tool for securing social inclusion for persons facing communication impairments.

As regards the term *communication impairments*, four sub-types are known in theoretical writings such as language impairments, speech-sound impairments, speech fluency impairments, and pragmatic (social) impairments.

Lindholm and Vanhatalo (2021: 12), when referring to the EL as ‘a form of accommodated speech or text: people being able (and willing) to adapt their speech to the reception capacity of the recipient’ admit that as of 2021, there is no ‘commonly agreed, official definition of Easy Language’. Nowadays, the EL has become an umbrella notion if referred to social work practices, and it is used to facilitate communication with people having special needs. Maaß, one of the leading scholars in the EL, defines Easy German as ‘a variety of a language that is particularly easy to understand and perceive compared to standard German’ (2020: 41–57). Considering the Latvian context, Anča, the Chair of the Latvian umbrella body for disability organisations (Sustento), who has launched the EL practice in Latvia, characterises Easy Latvian as a language variety of a standard language with reduced cognitive load to ease its comprehension through several grammatical changes introduced into the source text, as well as through revised conceptual structure and visual presentation of the text (Anča, 2001).

With the growing body of legislation on information accessibility, public authorities and businesses are required to provide information in the EL to ensure equal rights to all people who experience a need in this type of language. Thus, the significance of information accessibility is entrenched in legal acts at the global, EU, and national levels.

At the global level, ‘The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UN CRPD)’ was the first document that addressed the rights of people with disabilities. Article 9 (1) of the Convention establishes that

to enable persons with disabilities to live independently and participate fully in all aspects of life, States Parties shall take appropriate measures to ensure to persons with disabilities access, on an equal basis with others, to the physical environment, to transportation, to information and communications [...]. (United Nations, 2006)

Article 21 (1) on the freedom of expression and opinion, and access to information specified that

States Parties shall take all appropriate measures to ensure that persons with disabilities can exercise the right to freedom of expression and opinion, including the freedom to seek, receive and impart information and ideas on an equal basis with others [...]. (United Nations, 2006)

At the EU level, there are various documents and legal acts targeting information accessibility. For instance, ‘Directive (EU) 2016/2102 of the European Parliament and of the Council’ on the accessibility of websites and mobile applications of public sector bodies of 26 October 2016 focuses on accessibility in terms of principles and methods to be followed when designing, building, maintaining, and updating websites and mobile applications in order to make them more accessible to users, in particular, persons with disabilities. ‘Directive (EU) 2017/1564 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 September 2017’ permits the uses of certain works ‘protected by copyright and related rights for the benefit of persons who are blind, visually impaired, or otherwise print-disabled’. ‘Directive 2001/29/EC on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society’ is essential when adapting materials that are protected by copyright law but which are used for the benefit of persons facing intellectual and/or cognitive impairments.

At the national level, the requirements for information accessibility are stipulated in ‘Regulation of the Cabinet of Ministers of 14 July 2020 No. 445’ – the document that determines procedures for posting information on the Internet.

In compliance with the above-mentioned documents and to bridge the gap between the expectations of the community who experience the impact of cognitive and/or intellectual impairments in their adulthood, to advance social inclusion of these layers of society, and to satisfy the current societal needs and requirements, ERASMUS+ project No 2020-1-LV01-KA204-077527 ‘Promoting Easy-to-Read Language for Social Inclusion (PERLSI)’ was launched. It was carried out by the University of Latvia in October 2020, and it brought together an international body of stakeholders from Latvia, Lithuania, and Slovenia. Five out of six intellectual outputs of the project were aimed at developing EtR materials, with one intellectual output specifically aimed at EtR text producers.

The present study conceptualises the approaches for the development of EtR discourses at three levels, where the micro-level analysis is represented by selected intralingual strategies that are used to reduce cognitive load at lexical, syntactic and textual levels in line with Koller’s concept of pragmatic equivalence (2011: 251), the macro-level analysis concerns public discourse on information accessibility, and the meta-level analysis offers selected approaches used in pragmatics and clinical pragmatics for evaluation of the EL users’ language perception.

In addition, several aspects of pragmatic and discourse impairments in adulthood and some features of pragmatic language impairments were studied from the perspective of clinical pragmatics.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

1 THE TEXTUAL PRAGMATICS

Within the context of the present article and to analyse language use in communication, special attention is drawn to enabling individuals’ use of textual

function (Halliday, 1973, 2001, 2003). This can be carried out by employing a range of activities to ensure language use for text construction and text processing purposes in a written mode. Leech (1983: 57) argues that ‘texts have the function of transmitting the language’. Besides, he states that effective language use means meeting the communicative needs of language users, and, thus, the term *rhetoric* should be understood as ‘a goal-oriented speech situation, in which a speaker uses the language to produce a particular effect in the mind of a hearer’ (ibid.: 15).

Considering the above stated, Leech’s *textual rhetoric* principle is significant for the purposes of this study; it attributes the notion ‘principle’ to the meaning of ‘a rule that explains how something happens or works’ (*Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English*, 2014). Thus, the study examines how the rule specified can be applied for adapting texts intended for individuals having pragmatic and discourse impairments. According to Leech, the *textual rhetoric* principle is based on such maxims (also known as subprinciples) as: ‘the processibility principle, clarity principle, economy principle, expressivity principle’ (1983: 17). These principles underlie the rhetorical force of a text or utterance and, thus, reveal the processes that demonstrate how a textual transaction in a discourse is created. Leech suggests that any ‘discourse is the whole transaction, regarded as an attempt to convey a particular illocutionary force to the hearer’ (ibid.: 59).

Further, the principle of *textual rhetoric* is based on speaker-hearer / writer-reader cooperation, which, in its turn, is related to the phonological, syntactic, semantic, and pragmatic features that govern the text. The principle can be applied by making use of the *clarity principle*, which involves linguistic (i.e., grammatical, lexical) accuracy to avoid misinterpretation of the message, the *economy principle*, which involves the use of a selected and/or a specified amount of information applied for communicative purposes, and the *expressivity principle*, which involves the textual function to communicate linguistic messages.

For the purposes of this study, *the processibility principle* is considered in particular; it enables EtR language developers to convert texts to the EL intended for those individuals who have developed language impairments; this principle recommends that the text should be created in a manner that is easy to be perceived and processed within the time-framework that has been allocated for the task. In addition, this principle applies to the phonological, syntactic, and semantic aspects of the given text.

Pursuant to the processibility principle, the *clarity principle* should be taken into account as well. It seems to be efficient if used in a text construction process for the EL purposes, as the principle contributes to the transparency of the syntactic structures to avoid ambiguity (e.g., *If the baby won’t drink milk, it should be boiled* [adapted from Leech, 1983: 66]). It is evident that the danger of ambiguity lies in a confused interpretation of a statement or parts of the text.

The *economy principle* can be regarded as a valuable approach to condense the textual information or to keep the message ‘unimpaired’ (ibid.: 67). This

reduces the time- and effort-consumption for perceiving and producing the text, simplifies the text structure, and thus, enhances text production.

The *expressivity principle* can be considered efficient if used as an approach for the EL text construction purposes because it: (1) adds certain rhetorical value and enhances the use of language functions, (2) carries the effect of pragmatic implicature and, thus, ensures the development of the selected features of the textual pragmatics.

Thus, the above analysis indicates that the rules known as textual rhetoric principles can be adapted for constructing textual material in the EL for individuals having language impairments because the principles that govern the textual pragmatics, i.e., *the processibility principle, the clarity principle, the economy principle, and the expressivity principle*, can be used to reduce linguistic complexity and, consequently, the cognitive load of the written text.

2 INTERFACE OF DISCOURSE, PRAGMATICS AND COGNITION

Pragmatics as a field of applied linguistics has experienced notable changes since the beginning of the new millennium and has developed as an independent discipline. A remarkable number of scientific contributions have demonstrated the interdisciplinary nature of pragmatics, which can serve as a source for investigating the interactional and transactional communicative needs of language users. It should be marked that a discipline of clinical pragmatics has developed to meet the clinical needs of people who suffer from language impairments developed either in childhood, in the early period of adolescence, or in advanced adulthood.

To be introduced into clinical pragmatics, selected aspects of pragmatic and cognition interface should be considered. It seems important to state that people who have developed communication impairments experience problems with language use in certain contexts. Communication impairments cause both speech and language difficulties and can have a variety of manifestations, such as reduced vocabulary, limited sentence structure, and poor word articulation. In addition, people with communication impairments can face challenges in both inferencing the speaker's meaning from what has been stated (also known as pragmatic meaning) and in constructing the semantic meaning of a sentence.

At this point, it should be noted that limitations or inabilities of the language perceivers are in understanding the ideas expressed by the language users when the meaning should be inferred, or when the meaning is beyond what the individual sentences express. This is one of the conditions that develop the basis for discourse-pragmatic impairments, being manifested in cases when language users face difficulties with interpreting the literal (semantic) and/or non-literal (pragmatic) meanings (Cummings, 2015: 1).

In the situations referred to above, individuals, for example, may experience problems with understanding time concepts, temporal relations between concepts, use of speech acts to express language functions (greeting, thanking, apologizing,

expressing promise, threats or alike). Thus, discourse-pragmatic impairments often result in miscommunication; those language users who have developed these types of language impairments fail to perceive the implied meaning of a statement, they may be hardly able to share information with other interlocutors, or they may fail to perceive the illocutionary force of an utterance: e.g. A: *How was your trip to Riga?* B: *Everyone was sick in Riga.*

It is generally known that *discourse competence* in communication incorporates a variety of language skills and abilities. Individuals are expected to construct a cohesive text and coherent information flow in a discourse to meet the communicative needs of a narrative. On the other hand, *pragmatic competence* in communication may be demonstrated via an appropriately constructed text in a relevant context, where, according to Willcox-Ficzere (2018: 148), pragmatic competence implies the ‘ability to select/use linguistic devices [...] to achieve communicative goal, [and] ability to respond to interlocutor appropriately taking contextual factors (e.g., power) into consideration’.

As concerns clinical pragmatics, it is a relatively recent science (Cummings, 2014: 22–24) Even if the first writings on language impairments can be found in the late 70s’, clinical pragmatics has seen fast development due to many scholars’ contributions (e.g., Penn and Cleary, 1988; Cummings, 2014) whose research interest lies in examining such clinical conditions as specific phonological language impairments, autism spectrum disorders experienced in the early developmental period of a child, or in examining pragmatic and discourse impairments developed in the early period of adolescence, or in advanced adulthood, e.g., left-, right-hemisphere damage that influences language processing and production processes across the life-span.

Consequently, to understand how the above-mentioned impairments affect the pragmatic-cognition interface, it seems vital to view selected cognitive aspects that might be related to the development of pragmatic impairments. As regards the existing relationship between pragmatics and cognition, it should be admitted that language production and comprehension are not only related to the neuroanatomical structures of the brain that are responsible for language procession and ensure the language user’s production abilities but also to the linguistic disciplines that analyse how language knowledge is acquired and how the communicative needs of a person are satisfied (Cummings, 2015).

So far, this paper has marked that the knowledge of linguistic structures enables an individual to construct a word or sentence meaning considering the semantic features of the language, such as phonology, morphology, and syntax. To understand what has been meant by what has been said or how a text is constructed, and what cohesive links in a narrative are, one should be able to employ both discourse construction competences and the pragmatic appropriacy of language use. However, a person suffering from, e.g., clinical speech pathologies, pragmatic and/or discourse impairments, or cognitive deficits can hardly cope with making sense of a statement: persons having developed phonological impairments or adults with special language impairments can hardly identify meanings established

through a text or the use of semantic mappings (e.g., semantic fields). Coping with paradigmatic meaning relationship (e.g., use of idiomatic or metaphoric language) is a difficult task as well because such language use, as a rule, requires cognitive skill involvement.

A range of verbal and non-verbal behaviours, known as communicative appropriateness (Penn and Cleary, 1988: 3–17), enables an individual to assess the language skills demonstrated by another language user. It means that not only the use of formal language features but also the pragmatic strategies followed ensure a communicative event as a developed linguistic behaviour through (1) response to an interlocutor, e.g., expressed through the language functions of clarification, request to repeat, and alike, (2) control of a semantic context, e.g., expressed through the language function of topic initiation, (3) text cohesion, expressed through discursive elements, e.g., reference, (4) fluency of interaction, expressed through repetition, periphrasis, (5) sociolinguistic sensitivity expressed through politeness forms of language, e.g., addressing, parting, greeting, (6) features of non-verbal communication, e.g., facial expression (Cummings, 2015).

The above discussion has attempted to state that communication incorporates a variety of linguistic and para-linguistic abilities and their exposures. Consequently, it might be assumed that functional communication can be seen as an important feature to shape the treatment plan of individuals who suffer from discourse-pragmatic impairments to determine, e.g., the level of speech pathologies. Besides, the linguistic interventions can be examined not only through pragmatic language use but also through social language use. For purposes of ensuring individuals' pragmatic-social communication and depending on language impairments being established either in the early period of adolescence or in advanced adulthood, special emphasis should be laid on developing and expanding text/message comprehension and production abilities, on the production of a cohesive and coherent text, e.g., through implementing storytelling activities or alike. Similarly, individuals' communicative abilities can be reinforced through advancing simplistic linguistic strategies applied for, e.g., (1) setting questions, (2) responding to the questions set, (3) making one's needs and wants formulated, (4) leaving, addressing, or greeting someone.

DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS: DISCOURSE-PRAGMATIC APPROACHES TO EASY-TO-READ TEXT ADAPTATION

1 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND POPULATION

The research methodology was developed considering three theoretical contributions: (1) Bredel and Maaß's (2016) approach (cited in Hansen-Schirra et al.), (2) Darwish's (1999) process-oriented iterative adaptation model, and (3) Leech's (1983) textual rhetoric principle.

Bredel and Maaß's approach was applied for the analysis of the EL at three levels. It was used to show how the EL production can be enabled at three levels, namely, at: '*intralingual* with a diastratic orientation', *intersemiotic*, where visual processing is involved and *intracultural*, 'because source and primary target readers belong to the same para-culture, albeit often to different diacultural groups' (Bredel and Maaß, 2016 cited in Hansen-Schirra, Bisang, Nagels, Gutermuth, Fuchs, Borghardt, Deilen, Gros, Schiffel and Sommer, 2020: 201). The case studies below in the next part of the article illustrate how the approach can be adapted by EtR text developers for the consideration of intralingual, intersemiotic, and intracultural levels of EtR production.

Darwish's *process-oriented iterative adaptation model* was selected to reveal how the discourses envisaged for adaptation can be broken into three logical parts, (1) pre-adaptation stage, (2) adaptation stage, and (3) completion stage for reducing language users' cognitive load. By applying this model, the key stages were supported by ancillary activities; for instance, the pre-adaptation stage included such activities as planning and analysing the text type or language function, analysing the environment, and examining the required intralingual, i.e., diastratic orientation. The adaptation stage was implemented by applying the selected adaptation strategy and by introducing the necessary self-revisions to the first draft, by performing editing and proofreading, which, if possible, should be done by another person trained in EtR and by validating the first draft with end-users.

Leech's (1983) *textual rhetoric principle* demonstrated how linguistic and extralinguistic features across all stages of the EtR material adaptation process could enhance individuals' language perception and language production.

The empirical analysis was performed considering authentic texts on Latvia's State Forests website intended for adaptations into EtR. (Online 1). The corpus of source texts amounted to 10 000 words.

The research population consisted of two groups: permanent users and temporary users. The end-user group, which is rather heterogeneous, comprises two types of users such as permanent users, for whom the EL is a daily aid, and temporary users, for whom the EL is a stepping-stone towards reaching a higher level of language proficiency. The empirical material was validated with the permanent end-user group represented by people with intellectual and cognitive impairments. Validation, as Knapp (2021) suggests, is 'a process of assessing whether the content is, in fact, in Easy language or Easy-to-read [and where] end-users of Easy language information are actively included. [It] is often considered to be a crucial part in the process of publishing Easy-to-understand information'.

2 APPLICATION OF DISCOURSE-PRAGMATIC APPROACHES TO EASY-TO-READ MATERIALS

Maaß and Rink (2020) identify *linguistic*, *conceptual*, and *medial* strategies that can be applied for the production and adaptation of EtR texts. The scholars list such linguistic strategies as the choice of everyday lexis and short words, preference for simple sentences and reduced morphological load, when

explicitation of implicatures and presuppositions, explanation and exemplification of technical terms or less common lexical items, a simple argument structure of the text, addressing the audience directly and providing clear indications on follow-up action. (Maaß and Rink, 2020: 48)

The strategies identified by Maaß and Rink (*ibid.*) can reduce cognitive load at the lexical and syntactic level and ease text comprehension. However, Maaß and Rink maintain that the linguistic strategies alone will hardly reduce semantic complexity or exclude conceptual ambiguity. ‘To enlarge the common ground between authors and users of the text’ and to expand knowledge, such conceptual strategies as ‘knowledge development about the text or its sections, management of the cognitive complexity of the arguments and internal text or section structure, strategic orientation toward the prerequisites and demands of the target groups’ (Maaß and Rink, 2020: 48) should be used. The scholars draw attention to the significance of medial strategies in EL adaptations. They advise using such medial strategies as

typographic structure (indentations, medio points, highlighting), use of sign resources from different semiotic systems (visualisations, images, colour coding), connectivity between the sign resources from different semiotic systems. (*ibid.*)

The strategies mentioned can be associated with the implementation of the *processability*, *clarity*, *economy*, and *expressivity* principles discussed above at word, sentence, and text levels.

Thus, the *processability* principle, which entails three types of decisions (Leech, 1983: 67) to ease the comprehensibility and readability of the text, namely, the segmentation of messages into their units, the subordination or foregrounding of message segments, and the ordering of the message, is supported by the strategies recommended for the EL adaptation.

As stated by Ceplitis et al. (cited in Liepa et al., 2022: 86), special attention should be paid to grammatical categories of texts, such as predication, cohesion, integration, retrospection, and prospection, continuum, modality, auto-semantics, and lexical density. EtR texts are to be guided by *one main idea – one sentence principle* as well as are to avoid excessive detail and refrain from the usage of figurative language unless the text type requires it. Parenthetical insertions increase cognitive load and thus, if observed in the source text, are integrated into the text without the disruptive use of parenthesis. The information is to be organized sequentially. Long texts are to be divided into sections, and long lists are to be bulleted.

Referring to the above discussion (Ceplitis cited *ibid.*), it can be suggested that the EL principles can be compatible with the maxims of Leech’s *processability* principle. The *economy* principle entails reductions at all levels (Leech, 1983: 67) on the condition that they do not create ambiguity and meet the requirements for the EL adaptation. The EL rules advise reductions at various linguistic

and/or comprehension levels; for instance, it is recommended to reduce lexical complexity, morphological complexity, phrasal complexity, syntactical complexity, and textual level complexity in line with the conventions as pertains to the language used. The *clarity* principle associated with the transparency and ambiguity maxims (Leech, 1983: 66–67) is compatible with the EL linguistic strategies that enable the text developer to avoid ambiguity at the syntactical and semantic levels. The *expressivity* principle is backed up by an additional strategy in the cases when it is required to explicate the message in the EL adaptation.

Taking into consideration the above-stated, the analysis below demonstrates how Bredel and Maaß’s approach, Darwish’s process-oriented iterative adaptation model, and Leech’s textual rhetoric principle can be applied for adapting authentic texts in the EL.

As referred to above, the analysis is performed on authentic texts available on Latvia’s State Forests website and their adaptations into EtR (Online 1). The source texts are available in Latvian and English. The translation of the EtR Latvian segments into English is performed by the authors of the article subsequent to the adaptation into EtR performed by the project team. The end-user group represented by people with intellectual and cognitive impairments constitutes the research population.

For the purposes of this study, the paper adopts the translational term *source text* to refer to the authentic text intended for adaptation; the term *target text* is used with the reference to the text adapted for the EtR needs.

CASE 1

Case 1 illustrates how Leech’s textual rhetoric principle can be applied in the given sentences.

Table 1 Case 1

ST:	TT:
(1) <u>Latvia’s State Forests Nature Park in Tērvete is one of the most popular and family-friendly places for tourists in Latvia.</u>	(1.1) <u>Latvian tourists love Tērvete Nature Park.</u>
(2) It covers a total area of about 1200 ha, <u>a third of which is occupied by the Fairytale World</u>	(1.2) <u>The owners of the park are the company “Latvia’s State Forests”.</u>
	(2.1) <u>The park covers an area of about 1200 hectares.</u>
	(1.3) <u>The park is particularly suitable for family holidays.</u>

The adaptation is performed for the purposes of one of the deliverables within the project PERLSI. The first example is provided to illustrate how the *processibility*,

economy and *clarity* principles are used. The passage is marked to ease the recognition of adaptation mechanisms. Three propositions of Sentence 1 of the source text (ST) are marked by wavy, double, and dotted underlines, and the corresponding sentences in the target text column (TT) are marked respectively to demonstrate how these propositions are explicated in the target text. The marking of Sentence 2 demonstrates linguistic transformation, where each strategy is marked by a dashed and dash-dotted underline, respectively.

The ST segment holds two sentences. Sentence 1 contains three different propositions concerning Tērvete park. The first proposition introduces the owner of the nature park; the second proposition concerns the popularity of the park among tourists, and the third proposition refers to the park being a family-friendly area. Hence, following the *one idea – one sentence principle*, and in line with the *processibility* principle, the ST sentence is split into three TT sentences. Thus, the *economy* principle is implemented by reducing cognitive load at the syntactic level.

Textual complexity is resolved when relocating the sentence on being family-friendly to a further segment of the text to ensure its closer proximity to the mentions of infrastructure objects that would illustrate the ‘family-friendly’ area concept. This approach is used to reduce short-term memory load and promote readability among end-users.

As can be seen in Table 1, TT sentence 1.1. adheres to the *clarity* principle and restructures the possessive case introduced by the apostrophe + s (’s) structure in the ST. The TT explicates this condensed grammatical form by clearly identifying who the owners of the park are. Sentence 2 has undergone various changes to enhance its readability, too. The EL principles advise avoiding cross-referencing through pronouns because such cross-referencing might result in ambiguity. Thus, to reduce cognitive load and adhere to the *clarity* principle, the pronoun ‘it’ is substituted by the noun phrase ‘the park’ in Sentence 2.1, which is used repetitively throughout the text and ensures adherence to the *expressivity* principle because ‘the emphasis of repetition has some rhetorical value such as surprising, impressing, or rousing the interest of the addressee’ (Leech, 1983: 69). The dashed-dotted segment of Sentence 2 is cut out not to overload end-users’ short-term memory because the relevant information concerning ‘Fairytale World’ is introduced much later in the text. This approach allows the text producers to ensure the perceptibility and clarity principles.

CASE 2

Case 2 illustrates the approach taken to deal with the use of numbers in the EL discourse. The case demonstrates how Bredel and Maaß’s approach can be applied to the EL production at two levels, namely, at intralingual and intersemiotic levels, where linguistic and visual processing is involved. The selected example follows the same principle of coding as in Case 1. Three propositions of Sentence 3 are

marked by wavy, double, and dotted underlines, and the corresponding sentences in the target text (TT) are marked respectively to demonstrate information-processing mechanisms in the target text. Sentence 4 is marked by a dashed and dash-dotted underline for the same purposes.

Table 2 Case 2

ST: (3) Nature Park of <u>Latvia's State Forests</u> in Tērvete dates back to <u>1958, when the first walking trails were created in</u> what is now Sun Park. (4) Today, Nature Park covers <u>an area of more than 1200 ha, a third of which is occupied by the Fairy-tale World.</u>	TT: (3.1.) <u>About 60 years ago, the first walking trails were created in Tērvete.</u> (4.1.) <u>The park now covers more than 1200 hectares.</u> (4.2.) <u>A large part of the park is Fairytale World.</u>
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Case 2 contains two original sentences marked 3 and 4 in Table 2. The analysis demonstrates that Sentence 3 communicates three propositions when the general idea of the park is introduced. One proposition refers to the park ownership, which has already been reconstructed in Sentence 1 (Case 1) and should not be repeated in the given statement. The second proposition concerning the 'the first walking trails' involves the time reference '1958', and the third proposition concerns 'Sun Park', which is the geographical realia associated with the trails.

The three propositions being identified in Sentence 3 are reduced to one in Sentence 3.1., where the year 1958 is substituted with the phrase 'about 60 years ago' to reduce cognitive load at the semantic level and to assist end-users in establishing chronological links. Sentence 4 holds information on the total area of the park and reintroduces its thematic section 'Fairy-tale World'. Thus, it is divided into two sentences to communicate the relevant propositions. The full-form word is used in the TT instead of the abbreviation 'ha' provided in Sentence 4 to adhere to the *clarity* principle. A percentage share being expressed as 'a third of' is generalised into 'a large park' to reduce the cognitive load required for processing the whole-part correlation.

CASE 3

Case 3 illustrates the application of Darwish's process-oriented iterative adaptation model. It demonstrates how the discourses envisaged for adaptation can be broken into logical parts: (1) the pre-adaptation stage is represented as a source text (ST), (2) the adaptation stage is represented as a target text (TT1), and (3) the completion stage for reducing the cognitive load of language users is represented as a target text (TT2). The parallel threads for Sentence 5 in Table 3 apply the *expressivity* principle pursuant to Leech's textual rhetoric principle. The adapted target text

(TT1) has added the phone number where the source text (ST) just mentioned the opportunity to call up and book some services or facilities.

Table 3 Case 3

<p>ST:</p> <p>(5) A picnic area with a barbecue, benches, and tables [...] can be booked in advance <u>by calling the Information Center</u> of the Nature Park in Tērvete.</p> <p>(6) The net park is set in a pine forest and is unique in that it includes a wide variety of activities such as tree houses, trampolines, <u>basketball and ball courts</u>, two-level decks and net tunnels, all at an average height of 6 metres above the ground.</p>	<p>TT1:</p> <p>(5.1) There is also a picnic area. Please contact the Information Centre (<u>phone 28309394</u>) to book a picnic area in advance.</p> <p>(6.1) Tērvete Net Park is designed for active recreation.</p> <p>(6.2) It is located in the Land of Kurbads, next to a large car park.</p> <p>(6.3) The net park is created at a height of about 6 metres above the ground.</p> <p>(6.4.) It has tree houses, trampolines, <u>ball courts</u> and net tunnels.</p>	<p>TT2:</p> <p>(6.1.1.) Tērvete Net Park is designed for active recreation.</p> <p>(6.2.1.) It is located in the Land of Kurbads, next to a large parking lot.</p> <p>(6.3.1.) The net park is created at a height of about 6 metres above the ground.</p> <p>(6.4.1.) It has wooden houses, trampolines and net tunnels.</p> <p>(6.4.2.) <u>There are also areas for ball rolling.</u></p> <p>(6.4.3.) <u>These areas are bordered by nets.</u></p> <p>(6.4.4.) <u>Therefore, the balls cannot roll away.</u></p>
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In addition, the above example shows the approach of how the validation has allowed the EtR text producer to resolve the ambiguity of ‘ball courts’. To reduce ambiguity, the noun phrase ‘ball courts’ is substituted by the explanatory statements seen in Column 3 of the table above.

The above-provided case studies demonstrate the adherence of the EtR segments to Easy Language guidelines set for the Latvian language at lexical, syntactic, and textual levels, as characterized by Liepa et al. (2022: 103–132). The source texts are restructured into simple sentences without clauses; the sentence length is preferred not to exceed seven units of language. The EtR sentences start with the grammatical centre, where the subject and the predicate of the sentence are in close proximity. Long multi-syllable words are avoided, and eloquent units of language are not used.

CONCLUSIONS

The above-offered review of the theories and the analysis of the case studies enable the authors of the article to draw the following conclusions:

1. Easy language, being a variety of a standard language, can be seen as a language that reduces the cognitive load to ease its comprehension; it uses several grammatical changes introduced in the target text, a revised conceptual structure and visual design of the text.
2. The use of selected linguistic strategies can be observed in the adapted easy-to-read discourses:
 - 2.1 at the micro-level, i.e., at lexical, syntactic, and textual levels, to reduce the cognitive load of discourse,
 - 2.2 at the macro-level, to ensure discourse organization, information flow and its accessibility, and
 - 2.3 at the meta-level, to enhance the EL users' language perception and production.
3. To adapt authentic texts for easy-to-read discourses, the following discourse-pragmatic approaches can be suggested:
 - 3.1. Leech's *textual rhetoric* principle: being based on the processibility, clarity, economy, and expressivity principles, it determines the rhetorical force of a text or utterance and, thus, demonstrates the processes of textual transaction in a discourse created.
 - 3.2. Darwish's *process-oriented iterative adaptation model* explains how the discourses intended for adaptation can be broken into three logical parts: pre-adaptation stage, adaptation stage, and completion stage for reducing the cognitive load of language users.
 - 3.3 Bredel and Maaß's approach enables the analysis of the Easy language at three levels:
 - 3.3.1 intralingual analysis offers insights into the language used,
 - 3.3.2 intersemiotic analysis is concerned with examining visual processing of information,
 - 3.3.3 intracultural analysis has research interest in source and primary target readers who belong to the same para-culture or to different diacultural groups.

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